

Appendix: Capacitated Online Clustering Algorithm

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1 Appendix A: Dataset Description

We compare the performance of COCA and COCH against state-of-the-art (SOTA) on different *benchmarking datasets* described below:

–**Adult**- The data is collected from 32562 people comprising 21790 males and 10771 females during US Census 1994. The five feature attributes chosen for the present study are: age, fnlwtg, education_num, capital_gain, hours_per_week; and align with prior literature on clustering (Gupta et al, 2023).

–**Bank**- Marketing records of 411109 Portuguese campaigns. The dataset consists of 11568 samples from singles, 24928 from married, and 4612 from divorced people. The six feature attributes consistent with previous research (Gupta et al. 2023) are – age, duration, campaign, cons.price.idx, euribor3m, nr.employed.

–**Diabetes**- Data was collected over the last ten years from 130 US hospitals of 54708 male and 47055 female records. The feature attributes are age, time_in_hospital (Gupta et al, 2023).

2 Appendix B: Psuedo-codes and Image Flow

In this section, we provide pseudo-codes for different methods for the sake of completeness and better clarity. Furthermore, we provide an image flow for a better understanding of the proposed COCA.

2.1 Capacitated Online Clustering Heuristic (COCH)

The pseudo-code for the heuristic is detailed in Algorithm 3. The heuristic is motivated from LIB_H; along the same lines, we open the first $k + 1$ points as centers. Further, we also relax the logarithmic factors from the round update condition and set it as $q_r \geq 0$ and increment f_r by ten times.

2.2 Uncapacitated Online k -means (Fully online Algorithm, Liberty et al. 2016) (LIB)

We now provide code for the fully online algorithm as presented in [Liberty et al., 2016]. The fully online algorithm initiates by selecting the first $(k + 1)$ data points as the initial set of centers to estimate the lower bound on objective cost (w^*). Subsequently, for the remaining data points, the algorithm determines whether to assign each point to the nearest center or if the data point’s distance incurs a high assignment cost $d(x_t, c)$. This assessment is quantified using a probability that depends on the ratio of the assignment cost to the center opening

Algorithm 3 Fully online Capacitated Online Clustering Heuristic (COCH)

Input: Stream X , capacity parameter γ

Output: Centers C and assignment function $\hat{\phi}$

```
1: Initialize  $\Gamma \leftarrow \emptyset$  {stores vacant capacity of center}.
2: Open first  $k + 1$  points as centers and  $\forall j \in [k + 1]$  set  $\Gamma(c_j) = \gamma$ 
3: Initialize  $\phi \leftarrow \emptyset$ ,  $r \leftarrow 1$ ,  $q_r \leftarrow k + 1$ .
4:  $w^* \leftarrow$  objective cost on  $k + 1$  points using (Mulvey and Beck 1984).
5: Initialize center opening cost  $f_r = w^* \alpha / k$ 
6: for remaining  $x_t \in X$  do
7:    $c \leftarrow \operatorname{argmin}_{c \in C: \Gamma(c) > 0} d(x_t, c)$ 
8:   with probability  $p_t = \min(d(x_t, c) / f_r, 1)$ 
9:      $C \leftarrow C \cup \{x_t\}$ ;  $\phi(x_t) = x_t$ ;  $\Gamma(x_t) = \gamma$ 
10:     $q_r \leftarrow q_r + 1$ ;
11:   otherwise with  $1 - p_t$ 
12:      $\phi(x_t) = c$ ;  $\Gamma(c) = \Gamma(c) - 1$ 
13: if  $q_r \geq k$  then
14:    $r \leftarrow r + 1$ ;  $q_r \leftarrow 0$ ;  $f_r \leftarrow 10 \cdot f_{r-1}$ 
15: end if
16: end for
17: return  $(C, \phi)$ .
```

cost (f_r). To prevent excessive points from being opened as centers, value of f_r for round r doubles when the center count exceeds a predefined threshold. The complete pseudo-code is provided in Algorithm 4.

2.3 Uncapacitated Online k -means (Heuristic, Liberty et al. 2016) (LIB_H)

A heuristic approach is also provided by [Liberty et al., 2016] in which they initially open $(k + 1)$ data points as centers and compute w^* , by taking half sum of ten closest neighbours instead of the pairwise minimum distance between $(k + 1)$ data points. Further, they drop logarithmic factors by setting $q_r \geq k$ and increasing f_r by ten times instead of doubling it. Note that while LIB_H outperforms LIB but, it lacks theoretical results to support it. The complete pseudo-code for heuristic approach is described in Algorithm 5.

2.4 Image Flow for Proposed Algorithm

The image flow diagram for the better pictorial understanding of the proposed algorithm COCA is shown in Figure 2.

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Figure 2: Image flow for proposed online method COCA.

Algorithm 4 LIB (Liberty et al. 2016)

Input: Stream X

Output: Centers C and assignment function $\hat{\phi}$

- 1: Open first $k + 1$ points as centers.
- 2: Initialize $\phi \leftarrow \emptyset, r \leftarrow 1, q_r \leftarrow 0, n \leftarrow k + 1$.
- 3: $w^* \leftarrow \min_{v, v'} d(v, v')/2$
- 4: Initialize center opening cost $f_r = w^*/k$
- 5: **for** remaining $x_t \in X$ **do**
- 6: $n \leftarrow n + 1$
- 7: $c \leftarrow \operatorname{argmin}_{c \in C} d(x_t, c)$
- 8: **with probability** $p_t = \min(d(x_t, c)/f_r, 1)$
- 9: $C \leftarrow C \cup \{x_t\}; \phi(x_t) = x_t; q_r \leftarrow q_r + 1;$
- 10: **if** $q_r \geq 3k(1 + \log n)$ **then**
- 11: $r \leftarrow r + 1; q_r \leftarrow 0; f_r \leftarrow 2 \cdot f_{r-1}$
- 12: **end if**
- 13: **end for**
- 14: **return** (C, ϕ) .

Algorithm 5 LIB_H (Liberty et al. 2016)

Input: Stream X

Output: Centers C and assignment function $\hat{\phi}$

- 1: Open first $k + 10$ points as centers.
- 2: Initialize $\phi \leftarrow \emptyset, r \leftarrow 1, q_r \leftarrow 0$.
- 3: $w^* \leftarrow$ half sum of the smallest squared distances of points in C to their closest neighbor.
- 4: Initialize center opening cost $f_r = w^*/k$
- 5: **for** remaining $x_t \in X$ **do**
- 6: $c \leftarrow \operatorname{argmin}_{c \in C} d(x_t, c)$
- 7: **with probability** $p_t = \min(d(x_t, c)/f_r, 1)$
- 8: $C \leftarrow C \cup \{x_t\}; \phi(x_t) = x_t; q_r \leftarrow q_r + 1;$
- 9: **if** $q_r \geq k$ **then**
- 10: $r \leftarrow r + 1; q_r \leftarrow 0; f_r \leftarrow 10 \cdot f_{r-1}$
- 11: **end if**
- 12: **end for**
- 13: **return** (C, ϕ) .

Dataset	LIB	COCA	LIB _H	COCH
Adult	474.0±67.56	766.4 ± 107.53	12.8±0.6	13.8±0.87
Bank	522.1±71.14	737.5 ± 98.59	12.1±1.13	13.4±0.79
Diabetes	145.4±22.64	141.0 ± 13.59	12.0±1.09	12.8±0.6
Syn2d-(s)	197.5±56.34	212.9 ± 31.09	8.9±1.37	10.1±0.3
Syn2d-(o)	197.5±56.34	197.0 ± 25.82	9.3±1.01	10.3±0.45
Syn1d-(s)	137.7±108.37	82.2 ± 8.67	9.9±1.3	10.0±0
Syn1d-(o)	142.4±92.71	77.4 ± 8.94	9.8±1.24	10.1±0.3

Table 5: k_{actual} on various SOTA methods when k_{target} is 3 under uniform capacities (i.e., α is 1).

Dataset	LIB	COCA	LIB _H	COCH
Adult	806.7±93.32	1012.1 ± 133.66	20.0±1.34	21.7±1.18
Bank	886.1±115.89	1095.7 ± 133.58	19.7±1.48	21.4±1.2
Diabetes	195.8±26.97	170.5 ± 12.75	17.5±0.80	19.1±1.51
Syn2d-(s)	454.9±173.15	302.8 ± 35.08	12.9±1.3	16.0±1.48
Syn2d-(o)	454.9±173.15	339.8 ± 33.11	13.6±1.2	16.9±1.3
Syn1d-(s)	263.9±105.39	103.6 ± 18.34	13.4±1.68	17.9±3.38
Syn1d-(o)	241.9±88.46	102.7 ± 19.19	13.7±1.61	17.7±2.93

Table 6: k_{actual} on various SOTA methods when k_{target} is 5 under uniform capacities (i.e., α is 1).

3 Appendix C: Additional Experiments and Analysis

In this section, we present additional experimental findings to validate the effectiveness of our proposed methods. Initially, we examine

Dataset	LIB	COCA	LIB _H	COCH
Adult	1153.4±159.58	1220.5 ± 126.19	26.3±1.73	29.3±0.45
Bank	1311.6±137.23	1388.1 ± 180.04	26.4±2.01	29.4±0.66
Diabetes	214.4±25.81	163.8 ± 8.07	22.3±0.64	24.9±2.11
Syn2d-(s)	826.6±166.96	362.2 ± 41.35	17.9±2.62	23.4±3.50
Syn2d-(o)	826.6±166.96	390.5 ± 60.86	19.5±2.20	23.6± 2.53
Syn1d-(s)	401.1±168.74	123.2 ± 12.79	18.1±2.94	21.9±1.57
Syn1d-(o)	431.3±190.35	127.5 ± 17.51	18.4±2.61	22.0±1.18

Table 7: k_{actual} on various SOTA methods when k_{target} is 7 under uniform capacities (i.e., $\alpha = 1$).

Dataset	LIB	COCA	LIB _H	COCH
Adult	3143.1±866.86	2205.6 ± 251.65	54.5±5.46	60.9±0.3
Bank	3273.6±504.60	2325.3 ± 246.43	59.2±2.56	63.9±2.91
Diabetes	265.8±4.70	206.0 ± 7.94	50.7±5.86	47.9±2.80
Syn2d-(s)	2240.3±379.80	948.0 ± 126.29	51.6±5.14	57.4±5.00
Syn2d-(o)	2240.3±379.80	1031.8 ± 127.52	51.9±4.88	57.8±3.40
Syn1d-(s)	1536.4±904.62	292.8 ± 62.04	47.8±2.22	51.7±7.75
Syn1d-(o)	1603.2±1149.23	331.3 ± 71.18	46.9±2.54	48.3±2.83

Table 8: k_{actual} on SOTA methods when k_{target} is 15 under uniform capacities (i.e., $\alpha = 1$).

Dataset	LIB	COCA	LIB _H	COCH
Adult	4657.4±1060.78	2579.4 ± 258.59	77.1±5.37	81.0±0.0
Bank	4469.8±544.19	2867.3 ± 309.31	80.3±2.09	82.4±2.11
Diabetes	268.8±1.4	211.3 ± 15.58	71.5±7.81	66.4±6.74
Syn2d-(s)	3713.8±750.72	964.7 ± 110.01	65.7±4.63	62.6±6.29
Syn2d-(o)	3713.8±750.72	1175.0 ± 177.38	72.3±6.45	68.5±6.21
Syn1d-(s)	2136.1±674.30	451.1 ± 44.47	66.6±6.37	69.0±5.13
Syn1d-(o)	2141.2±432.02	498.7 ± 56.46	69.3±7.03	80.3±2.23

Table 9: k_{actual} on SOTA methods when k_{target} is 20 under uniform capacities (i.e., $\alpha = 1$).

Dataset	LIB	COCA	LIB _H	COCH
Adult	5946.6±1382.66	2858.7 ± 284.03	94.7±7.31	100.3±2.79
Bank	5571.2±701.10	3007.6 ± 256.45	98.6±4.94	102.1±1.04
Diabetes	270.1±1.3	224.4 ± 9.44	124.9±50.44	83.6±6.96
Syn2d-(s)	4939.5±1032.33	1117.0 ± 98.45	88.9±6.87	88.9±7.59
Syn2d-(o)	4939.5±1032.33	1365.3 ± 153.64	93.3±8.05	95.3±6.35
Syn1d-(s)	3565.6±1281.58	407.2 ± 55.26	88.9±6.87	72.9±7.32
Syn1d-(o)	3722.4±1478.66	443.2 ± 70.21	92.4±8.69	75.5±6.75

Table 10: k_{actual} on SOTA methods when k_{target} is 25 under uniform capacities (i.e., $\alpha = 1$).

Dataset	LIB	COCA	LIB _H	COCH
Adult	9865.8±1889.41	3594.8 ± 294.33	154.4±8.19	159.6±3.93
Bank	9516.1±1094.63	3744.7 ± 576.77	161.3±2.53	162.1±1.92
Diabetes	274.4 ± 2.53	323.3 ± 7.87	251.8±47.46	117.0±9.04
Syn2d-(s)	8872.2±1635.30	1756.2 ± 143.67	155.2±9.17	138.9±18.07
Syn2d-(o)	8872.2±1638.30	2134.1 ± 238.14	156.9±12.41	145.6±13.74
Syn1d-(s)	5744.6±1227.76	786.5 ± 74.76	155.2±9.17	117.1±16.94
Syn1d-(o)	5955.8±1470.21	801.0 ± 70.28	155.4±10.73	118.4±20.34

Table 11: k_{actual} on SOTA methods when k_{target} is 40 under uniform capacities (i.e., $\alpha = 1$).

the number of centers opened for left-out target values in the main paper under the uniform setting ($\alpha = 1$) (Subsection 3.1). Following this, we extend the evaluation to encompass the cost approximation analysis concerning capacitated k -means and k -median baselines, as well as offline uncapacitated clustering algorithms (Subsection 3.2). Additionally, we present results pertaining to the reduction in cost by a logarithmic factor in an uncapacitated setting, comparing COCA and LIB (Subsection 3.2.3), along with a corresponding comparison of the number of opened centers (Subsection 3.3). Further, we conduct an analysis of the number of centers opened for various capacity parameter values (α) in Subsection 3.4.

3.1 Analysis on Number of Centers Opened (Uniform Setting, $\alpha = 1$)

This section details the results on the number of centers opened by different SOTA methods on k_{target} of 3, 5, 7, 15, 20, 25 and 40 are listed in Tables 5 to 11. As can be observed from the tables, though the number of centers opened for the lower value of target k are slightly larger in a few datasets for COCA as compared to LIB due to capacity constraints. But as the value of target k increases, we see that COCA results in significantly fewer cluster centres than LIB. It is primarily due to our idea of opening enough centers in the starting to get a better estimate of the lower bound on optimal cost. We further note that the variance of COCA is significantly lower than that of LIB due to the doubling trick in estimating the number of points. When we compare LIB_H and COCH, we notice no significant difference in the number of centers opened.

3.2 Analysis on Cost Approximation

3.2.1 Comparison to k -means Clustering

We further validate our theoretical findings on the constant approximation of different online methods to their offline counterparts. To this, we compare our fully online algorithm (COCA) to its offline capacitated k -means (CAP_{kms}) (Figure 3 (a)). We further reproduce the result from uncapacitated online LIB to offline setting (k -means) (Figure 3 (a)). The Figure shows that our approximation factor ratio is near one for Adult and Bank datasets. For the Diabetes dataset, due to the existence of local minima and the fact that sometimes the offline algorithm gets stuck in local optima, we observe that the ratio is slightly below one. We further see that for the most number of the values of k_{target} , the ratio in the capacitated setting is lower than that of the uncapacitated setting. Further, we experimentally analyze the cost approximation factors of heuristic approaches in both capacitated and uncapacitated settings in Figure 3(b). Additionally, as an extended study, we even check how far is our cost approximation from online capacitated clustering COCA to offline uncapacitated k -means (standard vanilla algorithm) in Figure 3 (c) and obtain similar constant cost approximation observations.

3.2.2 Comparison to k -median Clustering

We also replicate all cost comparison experiments using the k -median update objective. In this context, we substitute (CAP_{kms}) with the offline capacitated k -median version (CAP_{kmd}) introduced by [Mulvey and Beck, 1984], and we replace offline uncapacitated k -means with offline uncapacitated k -median. The cost comparisons for COCA and LIB are presented against their capacitated and uncapacitated counterparts in Figures 4 (a) and (b). Similarly, for COCH andc, we present the results in Figures 6 (a) and (b). In summary, we note constant cost approximations, mirroring k -means setting.

3.2.3 Comparison in Unrestricted Setting

Here, we set $\alpha = k$ in our algorithms and assess their performance on cost. Particularly notable are the results in the cost comparison between COCA, and LIB, plotted in Figure 5 (a), (b), (c) and (d) which confirms a logarithmic reduction using the doubling trick. Note that here, we re-visualize the results for real-world datasets separately for enhanced clarity and additionally provide results on synthetic datasets.

Figure 3: (Left to Right): (a) Cost approximation of COCA to offline capacitated k -means clustering (CAP_{kms}). Additionally, provide cost approximation of uncapacitated online clustering heuristic LIB to uncapacitated offline k -means. (b) Cost approximation of COCH to offline capacitated clustering CAP_{kms} . Additionally, provide cost approximation of uncapacitated online clustering LIB_H to uncapacitated offline k -means. (c) Cost approximation of COCA to offline capacitated clustering k -means. Additionally, provide cost approximation of uncapacitated online clustering LIB to uncapacitated offline k -means.

Figure 4: (a) Cost approximation of COCA to offline capacitated k -median (CAP_{kmed}). Additionally, provide the level of comparison of cost approximation of uncapacitated online clustering heuristic LIB to uncapacitated offline k -median. (b) Cost approximation of COCA to offline capacitated clustering k -median. Additionally, provide cost approximation of uncapacitated online clustering LIB to uncapacitated offline clustering k -median.

3.3 Center Comparison for Uncapacitated COCA

We report the comparison between uncapacitated COCA and LIB on the number of centers for different k_{target} values in Table 12 to 21. Our observations indicate that, while for smaller target values LIB exhibits a slightly lower count of opened centers, the performance of LIB deteriorates as the target increases. This supports our choice to choose H_k as the initial set of centers compared to $k + 1$ points in LIB.

3.4 Number of Centers Opened on Varying α

We also evaluate the performance of COCA and COCH as the capacity parameter (α) is relaxed from 1 to 2.5, 5, 7, and k_{target} . The results are presented in Tables 22 to 31 for k_{target} values spanning from 2 to 40. Remarkably, we observe that the number of opened centers remains relatively consistent even as we relax the constraint on α from the most restrictive setting of one. This can be attributed to the fact that the online algorithms, whether capacitated or uncapacitated, open a sufficient number of centers to accommodate all points due to the unknown order of arrival of data points in the online setting. While there are a few datasets and target values where a slight difference (increase or decrease) in centers occurs.

3.5 Ablation on Variance of Cluster Sizes

In this section, we conduct an ablation study on cluster sizes for proposed COCA and LIB for uniform capacity and uncapacitated setting. The mean and standard deviation results for variance in cluster sizes across ten independent runs are reported in Table 32 to 41 for uniform and uncapacitated settings, respectively. The lower mean value indicates that across different runs, the variation in cluster sizes across all opened centers is not much and favourable in many instances, as discussed in the motivational example in the main paper. Note that in a uniform setting, we report results only for COCA as LIB is an online uncapacitated method and does not inherently accommodate capacity constraints. In an uncapacitated setting, it can be observed that the mean value is low especially on more challenging smaller k_{target} and perform comparably to LIB as k_{target} increases. Note that the COCA offers flexibility by allowing users to choose capacity constraints as per the necessity of real-world application.

Dataset	LIB	COCA	LIB _H	COCH
Adult	292.9 ± 20.79	578.9 ± 93.62	9.0 ± 0.0	9.0 ± 0.0
Bank	311.9 ± 33.29	509.4 ± 78.28	9.0 ± 0.0	9.2 ± 0.4
Diabetes	109.5 ± 15.18	131.7 ± 17.92	8.6 ± 0.79	9.1 ± 0.3

Table 12: k_{actual} when k_{target} is 2 and α is k_{target} for COCA, COCH.

Dataset	LIB	COCA	LIB _H	COCH
Adult	474.0 ± 67.56	763.2 ± 103.11	12.8 ± 0.6	13.8 ± 0.87
Bank	522.1 ± 71.14	736.5 ± 98.98	12.1 ± 1.13	13.4 ± 0.79
Diabetes	145.4 ± 22.64	142.3 ± 13.50	12.0 ± 1.09	12.8 ± 0.6

Table 13: k_{actual} when k_{target} is 3 and α is k_{target} for COCA, COCH.

Figure 5: Cost comparison of COCA (unrestricted setting i.e. when α is k_{target}) to LIB. The plot validates the theoretical cost reduction of a logarithmic factor on different datasets: (a) Adult, (b) Bank, (c) Diabetes, (d) Synthetic

Figure 6: (a) Cost approximation of COCH to offline capacitated k -median CAP_{KMD} . Additionally, provide cost approximation of uncapacitated online clustering LIB_H to uncapacitated offline k -median. (b) Comparison of cost approximation of COCH to offline capacitated clustering k -median. Additionally, the cost approximation of uncapacitated online clustering LIB_H to uncapacitated offline clustering k -median is provided.

Dataset	LIB	COCA	LIB_H	COCH
Adult	806.7 \pm 93.32	1010.4 \pm 133.40	20.0 \pm 1.34	21.7 \pm 1.18
Bank	886.1 \pm 115.89	1091.1 \pm 133.72	19.7 \pm 1.48	21.4 \pm 1.2
Diabetes	195.8 \pm 26.97	171.1 \pm 7.96	17.5 \pm 0.80	19.1 \pm 1.51

Table 14: k_{actual} on SOTA uncapacitated methods when k_{target} is 5 and α is k_{target} for COCA, COCH.

Dataset	LIB	COCA	LIB_H	COCH
Adult	1153.4 \pm 159.58	1213.3 \pm 131.88	29.3 \pm 0.45	29.3 \pm 0.45
Bank	1311.6 \pm 137.23	1392.5 \pm 178.84	26.4 \pm 2.01	29.4 \pm 0.66
Diabetes	214.4 \pm 25.81	164.0 \pm 10.23	22.3 \pm 0.64	24.9 \pm 2.11

Table 15: k_{actual} on SOTA uncapacitated methods when k_{target} is 7 and α is k_{target} for COCA, COCH.

Dataset	LIB	COCA	LIB_H	COCH
Adult	1857.4 \pm 206.12	1746.1 \pm 201.22	36.5 \pm 2.57	41.0 \pm 0.44
Bank	1969.5 \pm 205.36	1748.7 \pm 187.29	37.3 \pm 3.0	41.3 \pm 0.64
Diabetes	246.3 \pm 20.34	187.4 \pm 15.04	31.1 \pm 0.3	33.9 \pm 2.70

Table 16: k_{actual} on SOTA uncapacitated methods when k_{target} is 10 and α is k_{target} for COCA, COCH.

Dataset	LIB	COCA	LIB_H	COCH
Adult	3143.1 \pm 866.86	2208.3 \pm 254.00	54.5 \pm 5.46	60.9 \pm 0.30
Bank	3273.6 \pm 504.60	2324.0 \pm 249.02	59.2 \pm 2.56	63.9 \pm 2.91
Diabetes	265.8 \pm 4.70	204.3 \pm 8.96	50.7 \pm 5.86	47.9 \pm 2.80

Table 17: k_{actual} on SOTA uncapacitated methods when k_{target} is 15 and α is k_{target} for COCA, COCH.

Dataset	LIB	COCA	LIB_H	COCH
Adult	4657.4 \pm 1060.78	2566.2 \pm 256.22	77.1 \pm 5.37	81.0 \pm 0.0
Bank	4469.8 \pm 544.19	2863.4 \pm 312.30	80.3 \pm 2.09	82.4 \pm 2.10
Diabetes	268.8 \pm 1.4	211.1 \pm 13.07	71.5 \pm 7.81	66.0 \pm 6.55

Table 18: k_{actual} on SOTA uncapacitated methods when k_{target} is 20 and α is k_{target} for COCA, COCH.

Dataset	LIB	COCA	LIB_H	COCH
Adult	5946.6 \pm 1382.66	2857.4 \pm 275.42	94.7 \pm 7.31	100.3 \pm 2.79
Bank	5571.2 \pm 701.10	3002.1 \pm 247.06	98.6 \pm 4.94	102.1 \pm 1.04
Diabetes	270.1 \pm 1.3	226.1 \pm 8.45	124.9 \pm 50.44	83.6 \pm 7.07

Table 19: k_{actual} on SOTA uncapacitated methods when k_{target} is 25 and α is k_{target} for COCA, COCH.

Dataset	LIB	COCA	LIB_H	COCH
Adult	7136.4 \pm 1617.56	3075.7 \pm 268.01	114.7 \pm 8.1	118.7 \pm 4.00
Bank	6756.1 \pm 834.40	3490.7 \pm 320.93	116.2 \pm 6.24	122.5 \pm 1.5
Diabetes	271.5 \pm 1.74	254.3 \pm 12.89	198.7 \pm 75.14	93.4 \pm 2.24

Table 20: k_{actual} on SOTA uncapacitated methods when k_{target} is 30 and α is k_{target} for COCA, COCH.

Dataset	LIB	COCA	LIB_H	COCH
Adult	9865.8 \pm 1889.41	3592.0 \pm 298.70	154.4 \pm 8.19	159.6 \pm 3.92
Bank	9516.1 \pm 1094.63	3907.9 \pm 347.39	161.3 \pm 2.53	162.0 \pm 1.84
Diabetes	274.4 \pm 2.53	324.2 \pm 6.76	251.8 \pm 47.46	116.2 \pm 9.38

Table 21: k_{actual} on SOTA uncapacitated methods when k_{target} is 40 and α is k_{target} for COCA, COCH.

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$	$\alpha = 2.5$	$\alpha = 5$	$\alpha = 7$	$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$
Adult	541.7 \pm 79.80	498.0 \pm 73.71	515.5 \pm 79.13	533.1 \pm 82.67	578.9 \pm 93.62
Bank	544.3 \pm 82.69	504.2 \pm 76.26	545.3 \pm 84.54	533.1 \pm 82.67	509.4 \pm 78.28
Diabetes	143.5 \pm 16.55	152.6 \pm 18.67	127.0 \pm 15.47	137.7 \pm 17.06	131.7 \pm 17.92

Table 22: k_{actual} on COCA methods when k_{target} is 2 under varying capacity parameter (i.e., α values).

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$	$\alpha = 2.5$	$\alpha = 5$	$\alpha = 7$	$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$
Adult	766.4 \pm 107.53	766.4 \pm 107.53	766.4 \pm 107.53	766.4 \pm 107.53	763.2 \pm 103.11
Bank	737.5 \pm 98.59	737.5 \pm 98.59	737.5 \pm 98.59	736.5 \pm 98.98	736.2 \pm 98.98
Diabetes	141.0 \pm 13.59	141.0 \pm 13.59	141.0 \pm 13.59	141.0 \pm 13.59	142.3 \pm 13.50

Table 23: k_{actual} on COCA methods when k_{target} is 3 under varying capacity parameter (i.e., α values).

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$	$\alpha = 2.5$	$\alpha = 5$	$\alpha = 7$	$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$
Adult	1012.1 \pm 133.66	1012.1 \pm 133.66	1012.1 \pm 133.66	1012.1 \pm 133.66	1010.4 \pm 133.40
Bank	1095.7 \pm 133.58	1095.7 \pm 133.58	1095.7 \pm 133.58	1095.7 \pm 133.58	1091.1 \pm 133.72
Diabetes	170.5 \pm 12.75	170.5 \pm 12.75	170.5 \pm 12.75	170.5 \pm 12.75	171.1 \pm 7.96

Table 24: k_{actual} on COCA methods when k_{target} is 5 under varying capacity parameter (i.e., α values).

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$	$\alpha = 2.5$	$\alpha = 5$	$\alpha = 7$	$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$
Adult	1220.5 \pm 126.19	1220.5 \pm 126.19	1220.5 \pm 126.19	1220.5 \pm 126.19	1213.3 \pm 131.88
Bank	1388.1 \pm 180.04	1388.1 \pm 180.04	1388.1 \pm 180.04	1388.1 \pm 180.04	1392.5 \pm 178.84
Diabetes	163.8 \pm 8.07	163.8 \pm 8.07	163.8 \pm 8.07	163.8 \pm 8.07	164.0 \pm 10.23

Table 25: k_{actual} on COCA methods when k_{target} is 7 under varying capacity parameter (i.e., α values).

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$	$\alpha = 2.5$	$\alpha = 5$	$\alpha = 7$	$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$
Adult	1735.80 \pm 202.95	1735.80 \pm 202.95	1735.80 \pm 202.95	1735.80 \pm 202.95	1746.1 \pm 201.22
Bank	1751.4 \pm 191.69	1751.4 \pm 191.69	1751.4 \pm 191.69	1751.4 \pm 191.69	1748.7 \pm 187.29
Diabetes	189.0 \pm 16.05	189.0 \pm 16.05	189.0 \pm 16.05	189.0 \pm 16.05	187.4 \pm 15.04

Table 26: k_{actual} on COCA methods when k_{target} is 10 under varying capacity parameter (i.e., α values).

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$	$\alpha = 2.5$	$\alpha = 5$	$\alpha = 7$	$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$
Adult	2205.6 ± 258.59	2205.6 ± 258.59	2205.6 ± 258.59	2205.6 ± 258.59	2208.3 ± 254.0
Bank	2325.3 ± 246.43	2325.3 ± 246.43	2325.3 ± 246.43	2324.0 ± 249.02	2325.3 ± 246.43
Diabetes	206.0 ± 7.94	206.0 ± 7.94	206.0 ± 7.94	206.0 ± 7.94	204.3 ± 8.96

Table 27: k_{actual} on COCA methods when k_{target} is 15 under varying capacity parameter (i.e., α values).

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$	$\alpha = 2.5$	$\alpha = 5$	$\alpha = 7$	$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$
Adult	2579.4 ± 258.59	2579.4 ± 258.59	2579.4 ± 258.59	2579.4 ± 258.59	2566.2 ± 256.59
Bank	2867.3 ± 309.31	2867.3 ± 309.31	2867.3 ± 309.31	2867.3 ± 309.31	2863.4 ± 312.30
Diabetes	211.3 ± 15.58	211.3 ± 15.58	211.3 ± 15.58	211.3 ± 15.58	211.1 ± 13.07

Table 28: k_{actual} on COCA methods when k_{target} is 20 under varying capacity parameter (i.e., α values).

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$	$\alpha = 2.5$	$\alpha = 5$	$\alpha = 7$	$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$
Adult	2858.7 ± 284.03	2858.7 ± 284.03	2858.7 ± 284.03	2858.7 ± 284.03	2857.4 ± 275.42
Bank	3007.6 ± 256.45	3007.6 ± 256.45	3007.6 ± 256.45	3007.6 ± 256.45	3002.1 ± 247.06
Diabetes	224.4 ± 9.44	224.4 ± 9.44	224.4 ± 9.44	224.4 ± 9.44	226.1 ± 8.45

Table 29: k_{actual} on COCA methods when k_{target} is 25 under varying capacity parameter (i.e., α values).

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$	$\alpha = 2.5$	$\alpha = 5$	$\alpha = 7$	$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$
Adult	3071.1 ± 251.07	3071.1 ± 251.07	3071.1 ± 251.07	3071.1 ± 251.07	3075.7 ± 268.01
Bank	3485.0 ± 335.15	3485.0 ± 335.15	3485.0 ± 335.15	3485.0 ± 335.15	3490.7 ± 320.93
Diabetes	252.7 ± 12.46	252.7 ± 12.46	252.7 ± 12.46	252.7 ± 12.46	254.3 ± 12.89

Table 30: k_{actual} on COCA methods when k_{target} is 30 under varying capacity parameter (i.e., α values).

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$	$\alpha = 2.5$	$\alpha = 5$	$\alpha = 7$	$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$
Adult	3594.80 ± 294.33	3594.80 ± 294.33	3594.80 ± 294.33	3594.80 ± 294.33	3592.0 ± 298.70
Bank	3744.7 ± 576.77	3744.7 ± 576.77	3744.7 ± 576.77	3744.7 ± 576.77	3907.9 ± 6347.39
Diabetes	323.3 ± 7.87	323.3 ± 7.87	323.3 ± 7.87	323.3 ± 7.87	324.2 ± 6.76

Table 31: k_{actual} on COCA methods when k_{target} is 40 under varying capacity parameter (i.e., α values).

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$ (Uniform Capacity)		$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$ (Uncapacitated)	
	LIB	COCA	LIB	COCA
Adult	-	49.72 ± 11.92	80.61 ± 5.73	50.73 ± 11.72
Bank	-	62.71 ± 16.11	111.29 ± 12.73	59.64 ± 14.35
Diabetes	-	616.45 ± 26.87	730.16 ± 76.71	644.57 ± 66.70

Table 32: k_{actual} when k_{target} is 2 for COCA, LIB.

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$ (Uniform Capacity)		$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$ (Uncapacitated)	
	LIB	COCA	LIB	COCA
Adult	-	34.92 ± 7.04	55.76 ± 6.49	34.58 ± 6.96
Bank	-	46.18 ± 11.53	65.47 ± 10.13	46.23 ± 9.94
Diabetes	-	631.50 ± 36.26	626.80 ± 41.33	622.09 ± 40.77

Table 33: k_{actual} when k_{target} is 3 for COCA, LIB.

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$ (Uniform Capacity)		$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$ (Uncapacitated)	
	LIB	COCA	LIB	COCA
Adult	-	28.23 ± 5.17	33.93 ± 3.31	28.08 ± 4.97
Bank	-	31.64 ± 6.01	39.03 ± 5.79	31.56 ± 6.55
Diabetes	-	599.99 ± 18.73	575.16 ± 18.42	597.49 ± 12.60

Table 34: k_{actual} when k_{target} is 5 for COCA, LIB.

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$ (Uniform Capacity)		$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$ (Uncapacitated)	
	LIB	COCA	LIB	COCA
Adult	-	23.63 ± 3.56	24.60 ± 3.48	23.92 ± 3.88
Bank	-	25.53 ± 4.88	26.35 ± 3.58	25.57 ± 4.75
Diabetes	-	605.95 ± 10.87	562.95 ± 16.81	605.65 ± 14.63

Table 35: k_{actual} when k_{target} is 7 for COCA, LIB.

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$ (Uniform Capacity)		$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$ (Uncapacitated)	
	LIB	COCA	LIB	COCA
Adult	-	17.09 ± 2.66	15.25 ± 1.94	17.07 ± 2.63
Bank	-	20.86 ± 3.54	17.07 ± 1.98	20.50 ± 3.03
Diabetes	-	586.35 ± 18.39	542.34 ± 12.39	582.80 ± 11.72

Table 36: k_{actual} when k_{target} is 10 for COCA, LIB.

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$ (Uniform Capacity)		$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$ (Uncapacitated)	
	LIB	COCA	LIB	COCA
Adult	-	13.89 ± 2.19	9.48 ± 2.26	13.81 ± 2.11
Bank	-	15.62 ± 2.33	10.20 ± 1.74	15.55 ± 2.32
Diabetes	-	570.73 ± 4.90	530.63 ± 2.88	573.40 ± 6.35

Table 37: k_{actual} when k_{target} is 15 for COCA, LIB.

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$ (Uniform Capacity)		$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$ (Uncapacitated)	
	LIB	COCA	LIB	COCA
Adult	-	12.21 ± 1.61	6.15 ± 1.28	12.30 ± 1.66
Bank	-	13.04 ± 1.84	7.36 ± 0.95	13.12 ± 1.81
Diabetes	-	572.48 ± 12.70	528.87 ± 0.69	573.16 ± 12.71

Table 38: k_{actual} when k_{target} is 20 for COCA, LIB.

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$ (Uniform Capacity)		$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$ (Uncapacitated)	
	LIB	COCA	LIB	COCA
Adult	-	11.24 ± 1.44	4.87 ± 1.15	11.14 ± 1.45
Bank	-	12.50 ± 1.52	5.94 ± 0.84	12.51 ± 1.52
Diabetes	-	565.06 ± 7.97	528.23 ± 0.64	564.54 ± 6.47

Table 39: k_{actual} when k_{target} is 25 for COCA, LIB.

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$ (Uniform Capacity)		$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$ (Uncapacitated)	
	LIB	COCA	LIB	COCA
Adult	-	10.64 ± 1.15	3.99 ± 0.90	10.57 ± 1.10
Bank	-	10.95 ± 1.56	9.0 ± 0.0	10.82 ± 1.46
Diabetes	-	549.95 ± 10.01	527.55 ± 0.86	547.79 ± 8.47

Table 40: k_{actual} when k_{target} is 30 for COCA, LIB.

Dataset	$\alpha = 1$ (Uniform Capacity)		$\alpha = k_{\text{target}}$ (Uncapacitated)	
	LIB	COCA	LIB	COCA
Adult	-	9.13 ± 0.89	2.76 ± 0.57	9.13 ± 0.97
Bank	-	9.96 ± 1.05	4.9006 ± 0.71	9.97 ± 1.11
Diabetes	-	508.84 ± 5.07	526.12 ± 1.25	508.78 ± 5.27

Table 41: k_{actual} when k_{target} is 40 for COCA, LIB.